

Proposed Business Strategy to Increase Competitiveness of Deenay

Diara Qinthara Audini¹, Herry Hudrasyah², Ilma Aulia Zaim³

¹ MBA Student, School of Business Management, Institute Technology Bandung, Indonesia

^{2,3} Professor, School of Business Management, Institute Technology Bandung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: In Indonesia's highly competitive Muslim fashion market, Deenay, a significant player since 2017, confronts challenges such as declining sales, imitation product proliferation, and human resource issues, despite its robust capital and brand reputation. The purpose of this study is to develop and implement specific business strategies for Deenay in order to strengthen its competitiveness in the face of increasing market competition. Acknowledging the importance of capital optimization, boosting social media marketing, and resolving human resource challenges, Deenay is in a position to execute strategies that correspond with its unique market positioning and foster sustainable growth.

KEYWORDS: Brand Reputation, Business Strategy, Capital Optimization, Sustainable Growth, Social Media Marketing.

INTRODUCTION

Due in large part to the country's predominately Islamic culture, the Muslim fashion sector in Indonesia is an illustration of Islam's significant effect on numerous aspects of Indonesian life, especially when it comes to fashion. Islamic fashion, characterized by modesty, plays a central role in the Indonesian fashion industry, particularly embraced by women adhering to Islamic norms. The Muslim fashion industry in Indonesia has experienced substantial growth, contributing to the country's economic development. However, the intense competition in Indonesia's growing Muslim fashion business is highlighted by the struggle for customer loyalty. Established by Trini Midiati Yuniar in 2014, Deenay Styles & Scarves has had significant growth and development, emerging as an important player in Indonesia's Muslim fashion market. When the brand was first founded in May 2014, Trini and a small team handled the selling of ready-to-wear apparel. Deenay's growth into a well-known brand throughout time is evidence of Trini's commitment and business expertise. The brand's success is credited to its 2016 entry into the hijab production markets which allowed it to expand its product line and establish a reputation for distinctive geometric pattern designs.

Deenay faces challenges that necessitate strategic adaptations for long-term sustainability. Intense rivalry in the industry, compounded by the entry of numerous new brands, has impacted Deenay's sales. In 2019, the brand reached a mature and popular stage, but the impact of Covid-19 on demand caused a fall in the following years. On online retailers, fake products using the Deenay name have also surfaced, endangering the credibility of the brand. Additionally, the emergence of local Muslim fashion brands has shifted consumer preferences, creating a need for Deenay to modify its strategy to contend with new market dynamics. Additionally, the company's growth is hindered by the presence of unqualified human resources, especially family members in important roles that restrict company growth and competence. In order to overcome these obstacles, Deenay needs to update its business strategy, deal with the problem of imitation products, adjust to evolving consumer preferences, and make investments in highly qualified employees in order to maintain growth and lead the industry.

Deenay is owned by couple, named Trini Midiati Yuniar and Yadi Meifiadi, which Trini has a role as a director and CEO and Yadi's role as a General Manager in Finance Department. As a CEO, Trini is responsible for making decisions, target and making relationship with other parties for the partnership, and managing overall operations. Finance Manager is responsible for manage the financial operations of the company and ensure that financial company still stable. The role is essential to the business in order to allocate resources efficiently, implement cost-control strategies, and identify potential risks. Under the Finance Manager, there's accountant and tax officer for financial reporting in the company. The production manager's responsibility is to oversee and coordinate the company's manufacturing or production process. They are in charge of making sure that goods or services are produced effectively and efficiently while upholding quality standards and hitting production goals. The company have its own designer to ensure that the design for the product retains Deenay's personality and authenticity. Marketing is also the crucial role of the company since it's needed for building brand awareness and gaining customers. The department has social media officer, to

manage and execute social media strategies and creative team to create the content, photoshoots and event in order to attract customers and has to think out of the box.

Deenay, a major player in the competitive Muslim fashion industry, faces multifaceted challenges impacting its sales and market position. The industry's intense rivalry, compounded by the entry of new brands, has led to a gradual decline in Deenay's sales over time. The brand, established in 2017, reached maturity and peak popularity in 2019, but the landscape intensified with the emergence of local competitors and the disruptive effects of Covid-19 in 2020. The pandemic-induced decline in demand forced Deenay to reduce production and increase marketing costs to adapt to evolving industry trends. Additionally, the proliferation of fake Deenay products at significantly lower prices on e-commerce platforms poses a threat to the brand's authenticity, necessitating efforts to raise awareness among customers. Furthermore, a shift in consumer preferences towards local brands challenges Deenay's market position, requiring strategic adjustments to contend with new dynamics and competitors like Button Scarves, Wearing Klamby, and Heaven Lights. Moreover, the company grapples with the issue of unqualified human resources, particularly family members holding key positions, hindering professional expertise and impeding organizational growth. To ensure long-term viability, Deenay must renew its business strategy, address imitation product challenges, adapt to shifting consumer trends, and invest in qualified human resources for sustained growth and market leadership.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Brand Equity

According to Keller, brand equity is built through a series of sequential steps: brand awareness, brand associations, brand quality perceptions, and brand loyalty. Together, these factors form a pyramid of brand building, where each rung increases the brand's overall strength in the marketplace. This approach emphasizes how important it is to have a distinctive and appealing brand image that appeals to customers. The concept of brand equity is dynamic and ever-changing, representing the combined effect of a company's marketing initiatives, customer encounters, and business dealings. It is essential for shaping consumer preference, fostering brand loyalty, and maintaining a competitive edge (Keller, 1993).

Furthermore, the basic elements of brand equity could include both assets and liabilities. Both share a brand name and symbolize, which connects them, and they are grouped together into five dimensions. First among these aspects are brand loyalty; second are brand awareness; third are perceived quality; fourth are brand associations; and fifth are other proprietary brand assets (Aaker, 1991).

Brand Loyalty

According to Aaker's theory of brand loyalty places a particular value on the formation of positive thoughts and the steady purchasing habits of a certain brand over time. This implies that loyal customers not only repeatedly choose the same brand for their purchases but also hold positive perceptions and sentiments about the brand. These consistent behavior and emotional traits point to a strong and long-lasting bond between the customer and the brand (Aaker, 1991).

Figure 1. Brand Loyalty Pyramid (Aaker, 1991)

The loyalty pyramid illustrates five different customer loyalty tiers, each of which corresponds to a different amount of brand attachment:

- Disloyal Buyers (Switchers or Price Buyers): Customers with little interest in any particular brand are at the base of the pyramid. They have very little brand loyalty, and brands have little influence over what they buy. These customers are prone to switching products quickly and are frequently swayed by things like cost.
- Habitual Customers (Satisfied but Inert): Customers in this second category are content with the goods they use, or at the very least, they are not unhappy enough to think about moving. Their brand loyalty is fueled by inertia since switching brands would require more work and money, both of which would be obstacles. We call this group of consumers "habitual buyers."
- Satisfied Customers (Switchable): This third category consists of happy customers who, in spite of their satisfaction, are prepared to pay the switching expenses related to moving brands. These customers, referred to as switchable, are willing to make some compromises but are still willing to consider other options.
- Brand Friends (Emotionally Connected): The fourth level consists of customers who actually enjoy a brand and base their decision on symbols, pleasant memories, emotional connections, or perceived superiority. Known as "brand friends," these customers feel a deep emotional bond with the company.
- Loyal Customers (Committed Buyers): The most loyal types of customers are those who are proud to be linked with a particular company. They place a great deal of significance on the brand, both as a functional tool and as a representation of who they are. These loyal consumers show a strong and persistent brand loyalty.

Brand Awareness

Brand awareness is the ability of customers to identify brands within product categories in sufficient detail to make purchasing decisions, according to Kotler & Keller (2009). A consumer must be able to recognize a brand in many settings, which can be done by analyzing the brand's traits. Brand awareness is the capacity of potential customers to recognize and recall a brand for a specific product category, according to Durianto (2004). Following are the various levels of brand awareness:

1. Unawareness, in which customers are unsure if they are familiar with the brand mentioned.
2. Consumers can recognize a brand when they can do so.
3. Brand recall, in which customers can recall the brand even in the absence of outside stimuli.
4. Top of mind, which occurs when customers think of the brand when talking about particular product categories.

Perceived Quality

The customer's evaluation of a product or service's overall quality or superiority is referred to as the "impression of quality" dimension in Aaker's framework. The customer's evaluation of how effectively the product or service meets their requirements or expectations shapes this perception. In essence, the customer's personal perception of the brand's excellence and performance in fulfilling their particular requirements or expectations is reflected in the impression of quality (Aaker, 1996)

Aaker (1991) identifies a number of factors that influence how well customers perceive the quality of a product or service. These measurements cover both the actual features of the product and the overall quality of related services. The breakdown is as follows:

- a. Performance (Performance): Consists of the product's main functional features.
 - b. Features, or product characteristics: Secondary elements or additional parts of the product.
 - c. Conformance with Specifications: Determines the level of manufacturing process quality by evaluating the absence of defective products.
 - d. Reliability: This refers to the degree of dependence of the product for the intended purpose as well as the consistency of its performance over several purchases.
 - e. Durability (Resilience): Reflects the economic life of the product, indicating its longevity.
 - f. Serviceability: Shows that the business can offer services associated with the product.
 - g. Fit and Finish (Final Outcome): Indicates the moment when the product's quality is perceived or becomes apparent.
- The customer's view of the overall quality of a brand's products and services is shaped by these aspects taken together.

Brand Associations

As defined by Aaker (1996), brand association refers to all the associations and emotions associated with a brand. Not only is it important that these connections exist, but it's also important that they are strong. When a brand connection is based on numerous

exposures or experiences that successfully convey the brand message, its power is strengthened. The idea and what people recall about a brand are closely related. When individuals associate a brand with good memories or experiences, positive brand associations are created. On the other hand, poor brand associations arise when people remember unpleasant events or experiences connected to a brand.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research used qualitative research methods. This sort of research involves the collection, classification, analysis, and drawing of conclusions from the data analysis without the use of generalizations. According to Creswell (2012), a qualitative research study aims to discover and comprehend what people or groups believe to be a social or human issue. It is used to understand a social phenomenon's causes and mechanisms. The most popular techniques for gathering qualitative data in business research include interviews, questionnaires, and observation. Due to the fact that business is primarily a social phenomenon and that people are the primary source of information for performing business research, these types of data are employed as primary data (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016).

Primary Data

Primary data is information that has been gathered directly from the original source, without the use of an intermediary. Observations and subject opinions (individually or in groups) are examples of primary data (Sugiyono, 2018). Primary data for this research obtained directly from interviews that carried out with owner of Deenay (Trini Midiati Yuniar), Deenay's employees (Production Manager and Marketing Director), and loyal customer of Deenay.

Secondary Data

Information received by researchers indirectly through intermediary media (obtained and recorded by third parties) is referred to as secondary data. Evidence, old records, or historical documents often make up secondary data (Sugiyono, 2018). In order to perform this research, the author studied books, papers, and journals that related with Deenay's business issues. Company reports such as financial reports, sales reports, organizational structure, Deenay's social media are used as secondary data for this research.

FINDINGS AND ARGUMENTS

Resource Based View

A model called the resource-based view emphasizes the need of both tangible and intangible resources for achieving great company performance. The two types of resources are tangible and intangible, accordingly (Rothaemel, 2013). Referring to an interview with Deenay's owners, the company has tangible and intangible resources.

Tangible Resources

Tangible resources are assets that can be examined, measured, and have physical characteristics that make them visible (Rothaemel, 2013). These are tangible resource that Deenay have, following:

Financial Resources

Deenay established in 2014, the financial resources primarily from the owner's saving which used to initiate and sustain the business. Trini Midiati Yuniar as the owner build Deenay with her own savings and didn't borrow from other parties nor investor. With only limited budget that she had, Trini bought the equipment and materials with the cash that she had at the moment. At the beginning of the business, Trini hired two relatives as a employees for helping her build the business. She started and has grown the company with her own money up to this point. Deenay is self-funded; it does not rely on loans or have external shareholders who control a portion of the company. Deenay's financial resources have throughout time been further augmented by sales revenue, which has helped the company grow and endure.

Organizational Resources

Trini Midiati Yuniar established Deenay in 2014. Deenay initially only had three staff. Deenay currently employs 60 people, who are divided into a number of divisions, including a creative team, a marketing team, a production team, a finance team, and a warehouse. Deenay also has two general managers: Dewi is in charge of production, while Rani is in charge of marketing. Deenay's organizational resources are crucial for the daily management, administration, and growth of the company. The company's

organizational structure is shown in the existence of various divisions. This organizational structure makes it possible to organize and coordinate tasks and responsibilities effectively.

Physical Resources

The physical resources of Deenay, refer to the tangible assets and facilities that the company uses to support its operations and serve its customers. Deenay has one physical store that exclusively sells only Deenay products, namely Deenay Warehouse, located in Kembar Timur no 39. Within the same location as Deenay Warehouse, there is an office space. This office serves as the central hub for all of Deenay's business activities. It's where administrative and managerial tasks are carried out, including customer service, inventory management, marketing, and finance. Deenay has its own storage, which is also near to the store and the office, which is essential for managing inventory and product logistics. For daily operational, Deenay has own car, Honda CRV.

Technological Resources

Deenay use technology to their advantage in this digital age. It helps the business organize its marketing initiatives, boost online sales, and effectively handle sales data. Deenay used Instagram advertisements as one of their marketing strategies for digital marketing. These resources can offer information about consumer behavior, sales patterns, and the efficiency of marketing initiatives. Along with Tokopedia and Shopee, Deenay also maintains a website that acts as a virtual storefront for the company. A crucial part of online shopping, this website enables customers to explore the product catalog and get details about the brand and its products.

Intangible Resources

Intangible resources is resources that doesn't have physical attributes and thus are invisible. Intangible resources are assets that are embedded in the company for a long time. Human resources, innovation resources, and reputational resources are the three main forms of intangible resources (Rothaemel, 2013).

Human Resources

In determining the brand's identity, quality, and profitability, human resources are essential. Since they are in charge of creating the products that characterize Deenay styles, the production team at Deenay is the core of the company. For Deenay to drive sales, advertising, and acquiring customers, the marketing and creative team is equally crucial. They carry out tasks including content creation, product photography, and digital marketing for Deenay. The warehouse crew, which is in charge of quality control, packing, and distribution, is crucial for ensuring Deenay quality for its customers.

Innovation Resources

Innovation resources encompass brand's capacity to develop new products to stay competitive and adapt to changing market dynamics. Deenay's new collection that renewed after 3 months with newest design and color is one of innovation resources. They also innovate by working with influencers and having an exclusive collection. Deenay innovates in product development by using new kinds of fabric and material as well as enhancing quality to make the products more comfortable for the clients. By enhancing Deenay's website and online shopping experience is to improve customer engagement and convenience.

Reputational Resources

Deenay is recognized being a pioneer in the creation of geometrically patterned voal hijabs. Longevity in the market might indicate stability, experience, and a track record of exceeding client expectations because the brand had already been established in 2014. Deenay has a solid reputation generally, and its clients are aware of the high quality of the materials it uses. Deenay consistently produces high-quality goods over time. Since 2016, Deenay has had a legal license to protect its brand and trademark listed in HAKI Indonesia. This could improve brand integrity and consumer trust.

Capabilities

Deenay's capabilities are created by the combination of the tangible and intangible resources. These are the capabilities that Deenay has, following:

Financial

Deenay is now self-funded, which means that the owner's personal assets and resources are used to run and maintain its daily operations. This displays the capacity to run and maintain the company on its current cash flow. However, Deenay need an investor to funded themselves for their growth and if they want to expand internationally.

Maintaining Product's Quality

Trini, the owner of Deenay, is extremely conscientious and meticulous about the materials Deenay uses for its goods. Deenay is known for using materials of the finest quality in their products. Deenay never stops looking for the best material for the products they are about to release. Prior to choosing the material, it underwent a thorough process. To guarantee its quality, there is a team of quality controllers, merchandisers, and R&D.

Customer Service

Internet and social media used by Deenay as distribution channel and channel for interacting and communicate with customers. Deenay makes sure that its consumers receive the finest possible customer service by employing online platforms. Every complaint from a consumer will be addressed, and the problem will be fixed. Deenay also has this community and yearly event where reseller of Deenay would have a gathering.

Provide Product Knowledge

The team at Deenay is knowledgeable about the assortment of products and can instruct customers on a variety of topics, including fabric maintenance, styling options, and the distinctive characteristics of each hijab. The customer's buying experience is improved by this information. The creation of new hijab styles and themes is influenced by the brand's product knowledge. This entails keeping an eye on consumer feedback and market trends to develop items that appeal to the target market. Deenay's performance in the fashion sector is greatly influenced by its strengths in product knowledge. They make it possible for the business to deliver top-notch, innovative products that appeal to its target market, improving consumer satisfaction and brand loyalty.

VRIO Framework

A theoretical framework called the VRIO Framework is used to explain and forecast competitive advantage at the firm level. A firm can gain a competitive advantage if it has resources that are valuable (V), rare (R), costly to imitate (I), organize (O) to capture value of the resources (Rothaemel, 2013).

- **Valuable**

According to Rothaemel (Rothaemel, 2013), the VRIO Framework is an asset if it enables a business to raise the perceived value of its goods in the eyes of consumers, either by including alluring features or by reducing the price since the resource enables the business to cut costs. Deenay has a solid reputation for employing high-quality materials in its products. This reputation is beneficial since it might draw in and attract customers who are looking for high-quality hijab accessories. Deenay has a valuable proposition: offering premium goods at reasonable prices. It could improve Deenay's competitive position by making its products more accessible to a wider variety of customers. Another element is Deenay being one of the first brands that sells hijabs with geometrical patterns in the market.

- **Rare**

Rare is described as a resource or capability that only one or a small number of organizations possess or can do in the same way. No company will be able to sustain a competitive advantage if the resource or capability is widely available (Rothaemel, 2013). Resources and abilities like those of Deenay are common. This is because both established manufacturers and newcomers can easily embrace the characteristics of conducting business in the Muslim fashion industry, notably in Indonesia. Although Deenay stands out as an innovation thanks to its use of geometric designs in voal hijabs, the brand faces competition from a number of brands, including Button Scarves, Wearing Klamby, Heaven Lights, Kami Idea, Dian Pelangi, Indah Nada Puspita, and others, who also produce and sell printed scarves.

- **Cost to Imitiate**

If a business that does not own the resource is unable to produce or purchase the resource at a comparable price, it is said to be costly to imitate (Rothaemel, 2013). It is fairly easy to copy Deenay's products, especially hijabs. This is so because neither a sizable financial investment nor cutting-edge technology are needed for the production process. Deenay's hijab designs are also easy to

duplicate, and there are instances of imitation in the market. There are many fake goods in the market with the name "Deenay" and with similar designs. Additionally, inexpensive goods from nations like China can easily copy Deenay's designs and reach the Indonesian market without facing significant financial obstacles.

Organize to Capture Value

To fully utilize the competitive potential of the firm's resources and capabilities, an effective organizational structure and coordinating systems must be in place (Rothaemel, 2013). This is what is meant by "organize to capture value." Trini has a key role in the company's leadership and decision-making processes and is the sole owner of all of Deenay's shares. Deenay is regarded as a small business with a decentralized management system. This structure often places a strong emphasis on adaptability, flexibility, and open communication. Managers for marketing and production are present, indicating a disciplined approach to managing major operational areas. These managers assist in the execution of plans in the areas they specialize in while Trini takes overall decisions. With 60 employees, Deenay has the human resources required to manage and execute daily operations efficiently. This employee base supports the firm's organized approach to business.

In summary, even though Deenay has substantial resources, its competitive edge is limited by the market's lack of rarity and the simplicity of imitation. Although Deenay's reputation, pricing policy, and distinctive designs are key assets, it is difficult to keep a competitive advantage given the dynamics of the Indonesian Muslim fashion market. Deenay might need to concentrate on continual innovation, branding, and differentiation initiatives in order to grow and maintain its position as a leader in a crowded market. It indicates that Deenay have Competitive Parity.

SWOT Analysis

A SWOT analysis, according to Summut-Bonnici and Galea (2014), assesses both benefits and risks that are external to a business as well as its internal strengths and weaknesses. The organization's internal resources, competencies, and competitive advantages are determined through internal analysis. The external study looks at the resources of competitors, the industry environment, and the overall environment to identify market opportunities and threats. Following an in-depth examination, this following SWOT analyses are based on internal and external analysis.

Table 1. SWOT Analysis for Deenay

<p>Strengths:</p> <p>(S1) Has a strong brand reputation</p> <p>(S2) Good quality of the material</p> <p>(S3) Have own physical stores in Bandung and Jakarta.</p> <p>(S4) Have strong relationship with suppliers</p> <p>(S5) Strong capital and healthy financial performance</p> <p>(S6) Strong value chain</p> <p>(S7) High loyalty of resellers</p>	<p>Weaknesses:</p> <p>(W1) Unqualified human resources</p> <p>(W2) No protection to their design so it easily imitated</p> <p>(W3) Physical stores still limited in West Java</p> <p>(W4) Lack of activation event for marketing strategy</p>
<p>Opportunities:</p> <p>(O1) Increasing number of women who wearing hijab and dress modest</p> <p>(O2) Increasing economic capability of Indonesia</p> <p>(O3) High amount of Muslim in Indonesia</p> <p>(O4) Indonesians use social media significantly on a daily basis.</p> <p>(O5) Easy connections with vendors</p> <p>(O6) High interest to Fashion Muslim in the global market</p>	<p>Threats:</p> <p>(T1) High competitive industry in Muslim fashion</p> <p>(T2) Dynamics fashion trends that easily change</p> <p>(T3) Imitation product of Deenay</p>

TOWS Matrix

In addition to developing alternate tactics, Wehrich (1982) developed the TOWS matrix as the next step after the SWOT analysis. The TOWS matrix provides a means of formulating strategies that logically integrate elements associated with opportunities or threats from the external environment with aspects linked to internal strengths or weaknesses (Ravanvar & Charantimath, 2012). The previous SWOT analysis was used to build the TOWS matrix, which is displayed in the table below.

Table 2. TOWS Matrix

	Strengths	Weaknesses
Opportunities	<p>(SO1) – (S1, S2, S5, O5) Focus on optimizing social media marketing</p> <p>(SO2) – (S1, S3, S5, O1, O2, O4) Utilizing capital to expanding the market</p> <p>(SO3) – (S1, S2, S5, S6, O1, O5, O6) Partnering with vendors that has connection to global market</p>	<p>(WO1) – (W2, W4, O1, O3, O5) Increasing brand awareness</p> <p>(WO2) – (W4, O3, O4) Enhance digital marketing strategy</p> <p>(WO3) – (W4, O1, O2, O3, O5) Develop a monthly calendar of activation event.</p>
Threats	<p>(ST1) –(S1, S2, S3, S4, S5, S6, T1, T2) Mitigate competitive industry through differentiation</p> <p>(ST2) –(S1, S2, S5, S6, T1) Collaboration with strong public figure for a new product</p>	<p>(WT1) – (W1, W4, T1, T2, T3) Investing on traning program and to hire qualified and creative employees.</p> <p>(WT2) – (W2, T1, T3) Implement a measures for imitation products</p> <p>(WT3) – (W1, T1, T2) Conduct a regular trend analysis to stay ahead of industry changes.</p>

Using the company's strengths, such as a strong brand reputation, high-quality components, physical stores in prime locations like Bandung and Jakarta, solid supplier relationships, plenty of capital, and strong financial performance—is a key component of Deenay's strategic approach. The goal is to carefully and not only make use of these benefits in order to seize emerging possibilities. This entails making the most of social media marketing campaigns, making smart use of the available resources for market development in accordance with government-backed programs, and establishing international alliances with suppliers to investigate other markets. In addition to taking advantage of the opportunities that present themselves, the focus is on laying the groundwork for future growth and relevance.

Strength & Opportunities (SO)

- **SO1 – Optimizing social media marketing**

Make use of Deenay's strong financial health, excellent brand reputation, and superior resources to create a successful social media marketing strategy. This involves utilizing popular social media platforms such as TikTok and Instagram to accentuate Deenay's strengths and enhance engagement. To execute this strategy, Deenay should establish a dedicated social media team tasked with creating compelling weekly fashion content. This team will actively engage with customers, fostering a sense of community while effectively promoting Deenay's products.

- **SO2 - Utilizing capital to expanding the market**

Given Deenay's robust financial performance and self-funded status, there exists a significant opportunity to leverage these resources to expand its market presence. The company has the potential to strategically expand its reach beyond West Java and become a reputable national brand. This regional expansion serves as a crucial initial phase before contemplating international ventures. Furthermore, by using an attractive and unique concept, Deenay can maximize its physical outlets in more cities like Sumatera and Kalimantan area. This approach aims to captivate customers, encouraging them to visit the physical stores not just for online purchases but also to experience the brand and its products firsthand. Implementing a distinctive in-store concept can contribute to brand visibility and customer loyalty.

- **SO3 - Partnering with vendors that has connection to global market**

The approach involves creating strategic partnerships with suppliers who have links to international markets in order to use Deenay's strong value chain, high-quality material, positive financial performance, and strong brand reputation. This approach aims to extend Deenay's reach beyond domestic borders and tap into the international Muslim fashion market. By leveraging its existing strengths, Deenay can benefit from the expertise and networks of these global vendors, ensuring seamless integration into the international fashion landscape. The collaboration aims to enhance Deenay's visibility and accessibility in the global market, ultimately positioning it as a prominent player in the evolving Muslim fashion industry on a worldwide scale.

Weakness & Opportunities (WO)

- **WO1 – Increasing brand awareness**

In order to address the issues related to inadequate human resources and a limited number of physical stores, the strategy requires the execution of focused campaigns aimed at raising awareness of the brand. Comprehensive digital marketing efforts, partnerships with influencers, and presence at events that appeal to the target demographic are a few examples of the approaches.

- **WO2 - Enhance digital marketing strategy**

In the modern, digitalized world, everyone must stay ahead of the trends and consistently produce innovative ideas that effectively combine creativity and technology. It is essential to use targeted advertisements on social media networks and optimize a personal website. This guarantees that Deenay focuses on giving people an engaging online experience rather than just selling products.

- **WO3 – Monthly activation events**

One of the strategies the author suggested Deenay use is monthly activation events to raise awareness of the brand, loyalty to the brand, and brand associations. Arranging a monthly activation event, such as a get-together with Deenay's loyal customers and resellers, taking part in fashion shows or exhibition, collaborating with influencers, and partnering with a brand on events like workshops and sports events.

Strength & Threats (ST)

- **ST1- Mitigating competitive industry**

To effectively mitigate competitive threats and solidify Deenay's position in the Muslim fashion industry, the company can implement a comprehensive strategy centered on differentiation. By capitalizing on its strong brand image, high-quality material, and strong value chain, Deenay needs to concentrate on differentiating itself from competitors. This can be accomplished by continuously providing unique and cutting-edge designs that appeal to the specific market, making sure that the goods are notable for their outstanding quality and unique style. Working together with well-known designers or influencers can improve Deenay's products' exclusivity even more. Furthermore, highlighting sustainable and ethical production methods can help create a unique brand identity. By strategically differentiating its products, Deenay can effectively navigate the competitive landscape, attract a loyal customer base, and maintain a stronghold in the Muslim fashion industry.

- **ST2 – Collaboration for new product**

Strategic partnerships with well-known influencers and designers tailored to Deenay's target market can significantly elevate brand awareness and foster innovation. In order to succeed in entering global markets like Malaysia and Singapore, Deenay needs to overcome conventional boundaries. Product design, packaging, and partnerships with internationally renowned public figures have to be enhanced. By aligning with influential figures who have an international presence, Deenay can amplify its brand visibility and appeal to a broader audience. These collaborations not only contribute to the development of high-quality, trendsetting products but also open doors to new market segments.

Weakness & Threats (WT)

- **WT1 – Training program and hiring qualified employees**

In order to improve the level of quality and creativity of Deenay's products, a comprehensive training program and the thoughtful recruitment of qualified employees are required. Investing in employee development is a cornerstone for fostering innovation and maintaining high standards. Employee skill development and industry knowledge may be maintained through specific training programs, guaranteeing Deenay's leadership position in the fast-paced Muslim fashion market. At the same time, the company will gain fresh insights by hiring competent experts in design, marketing, and business operations. Deenay may strengthen its market position, boost product quality, and skillfully manage the difficulties of a competitive industry by creating an educated and competent team.

- **WT2 – Implement measures for imitation products**

Anticipating and combating imitation products requires a thorough strategy in order to protect Deenay's original designs and intellectual property. To safeguard the brand's designs, trademarks, and other intellectual property, legal action must be taken. Educating both employees and customers about the importance of originality and the potential consequences of purchasing or producing imitation products is crucial. Moreover, implementing advanced technologies such as anti-counterfeiting measures and blockchain in the supply chain can provide transparency and traceability, further deterring the production and sale of imitation Deenay products.

- **WT3 – Trend analysis for dynamic industry changes**

Given how quickly the Muslim fashion industry is changing, Deenay ought to provide a strategic focus on trend analysis. By closely monitoring and analyzing market trends, fashion preferences, and consumer behavior, Deenay can proactively adapt its designs and offerings to stay ahead of industry changes. To ensure a thorough grasp of new trends and customer demands, this method requires creating specialized teams or collaborating with trend analysis specialists.

CONCLUSION

Deenay Styles & Scarves exhibits several internal strengths, such as a good reputation of the brand, premium materials, strong supplier relationships, excellent financial performance, a well-established value chain, and high reseller loyalty. However, Deenay has to deal with issues such as inadequate human resources, lack of design protection, limited offline stores, and a lack of marketing activation events and social media. External opportunities include a growing number of women wearing hijab and dress modest, a large Muslim population, widespread social media use, easy connections with suppliers, and a global interest in Muslim fashion. On the other hand, Deenay faces challenges from a market that is highly competitive with a lot of new entrants, constantly changing fashion trends and the imitation products of Deenay.

Deenay can implement the proposed business strategy through a structured and phased approach. In order to address the problem of underqualified human resources, it should first engage in extensive training programs to make sure that its personnel has the skills required to produce innovative and high-quality products. Deenay should safeguard its designs with intellectual property rights at the same time to reduce the possibility of imitation products. The expansion of physical stores, particularly in areas beyond West Java, demands careful market research and strategic partnerships with malls or retail chains. Deenay could set up a specialized team for social media content development in order to improve digital marketing, guaranteeing a dependable and interesting online presence. Collaborations with influencers and designers should be pursued strategically, aligning with the brand's target market.

REFERENCES

1. Aaker, D. A. (1991). *Managing brand equity*. https://openlibrary.org/books/OL1532721M/Managing_brand_equity
2. Aaker, D. A. (1996). Measuring brand equity across products and markets. *California Management Review*, 38(3), 102-120.
3. Creswell, J. W. (1994). *Research Design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. http://www.revistacomunicacion.org/pdf/n3/resenas/research_design_qualitative_quantitative_and_mixed_methods_approaches.pdf
4. Durianto, D. (2004). *Strategy to Conquer the Market through Equity and Behavioral Research*. Gramedia.

5. Keller, K. L. (1993). Conceptualizing, Measuring, and Managing Customer-Based Brand Equity. *Journal of Marketing*, 57(1), 1–22.
6. Kotler, Philip & Gerry Armstrong, (2014): *Principle Of Marketing*, 15th edition. New Jersey: Pearson Pretice Hall.
7. Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2009). *Marketing Management* (13th editi). Erlangga.
8. Ravanvar, G. M., & Charantimath, P. M. (2012, July). Strategic Formulation Using Tows Matrix – A Case Study. *International Journal of Research and Development*, 87-90.
9. Rothaemel, F.T. (2013). *Strategic Management Concept*. New York: *The McGraw-Hill*.
10. Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods For Business: A skill building approach* (seventh ed). John Wiley & Sons. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-007-0753-5_102084
11. Sugiyono. (2017). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
12. Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kombinasi (Mixed Methods)*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
13. Sammut-Bonnici, T., & Galea, D. (2014). SWOT Analysis. In C. Cooper (Ed.), *Wiley Encyclopedia of Management* (Vols. 12 - Strategic Management). John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. doi:10.1002/9781118785317.weom120103
14. Volberda, H., Morgan, R. E., Reinmoeller, P., Hitt, M. A., Ireland, R. D., & Hoskisson, R. E. (2011). Strategic Management: Competitiveness and Globalization (Concepts & Cases). In *Cengage Learning eBooks*. <http://orca.cf.ac.uk/25299/>
15. Wehrich, H. (1982). The TOWS matrix—A tool for situational analysis. *Long Range Planning*, 15(2), 54–66. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301\(82\)90120-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0024-6301(82)90120-0)
16. Wijayanti, T. (2017). *Marketing Plan Dalam Bisnis* (3rd ed.). Jakarta: Alex Media Komputindo.

Cite this Article: Diara Qinthara Audini, Herry Hudrasyah, Ilma Aulia Zaim (2024). Proposed Business Strategy to Increase Competitiveness of Deenay. *International Journal of Current Science Research and Review*, 7(1), 307-317